

ARRIVE Essential 10 Checklist

1. Study Design: Randomized controlled experimental study using male rats.
2. Sample Size: Sample size justified based on similar published studies.
3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Healthy adult male rats included.
4. Randomisation: Animals randomly assigned to groups.
5. Blinding: Outcome assessment conducted blinded where possible.
6. Outcome Measures: Liver and kidney function biomarkers.
7. Statistical Methods: ANOVA and post-hoc tests used.
8. Experimental Animals: Species, strain, sex, age, and weight reported.
9. Experimental Procedures: Orlistat dosing, diet composition, duration provided.
10. Results: All outcomes reported with variability and n values.